

ADPOSITION IN AFRICAN LANGUAGES

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1 Introduction

The present paper has a twofold purpose. On the one hand it is concerned with the conceptual input of grammaticalization, and on the other with its linguistic output.² It will be argued that in specific cases it is possible to determine both the range of possible source structures serving as the input and the nature of linguistic

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2. We will use the by now "classical" definition volunteered by Kurylowicz (1965:52) according to which grammaticalization "consists in the increase of the range of a morpheme advancing from a lexical to a grammatical or from a less grammatical to a more grammatical status...". This process is assumed to be *unidirectional*. For more details, see Heine, Claudi & Hünemeyer *forthc.*, Section 1.

structures emerging as a result of the grammaticalization process.

Our concern in this paper is exclusively with five cognitive units referred to by means of the conceptual labels ON, UNDER, FRONT, BACK and IN.³ These relational concepts of spatial orientation are distinguished in all African languages known to us, although there exists an enormous diversity in the way they are encoded morphologically and syntactically.

2 Morphosyntax

2.1 Terminology

In some grammars of African languages one finds statements like "Language X does not have prepositions but only postpositions", or even "The prepositions of language X will be called postpositions because they follow the noun". Lyons (1967:302) observes that the difference between prepositions and postpositions is trivial and that "many linguists would say that it is mere pedantry to maintain the terminological distinction". Research on the order of meaningful elements carried out four years earlier (Greenberg 1963b) had established that this terminology is not all that trivial. In the following treatment, we will distinguish between prepositions and postpositions where this is necessary; otherwise we will use the label "adposition" as a cover term for both.

As is shown below, there is considerable confusion in grammars on African languages as to what is called an adposition. Grammars written prior to World War II frequently contain a distinct paragraph or chapter devoted

3. These five labels stand for a number of closely related lexemes like *above, over, on top of, up* (for ON), *down, below* (for UNDER), *before, in front of, ahead* (for FRONT), *behind, after* (for BACK), and *inside, within* (for IN), respectively.

to prepositions. More recently, however, this term is seldom made use of in descriptions of African languages; in fact, in quite a few grammars it does not figure at all. This is due to developments in theoretical linguistics which no longer take it for granted, e.g., that African languages can be described in terms of word categories commonly distinguished in European languages.

This change in outlook and terminology, however, has not always made access to grammars of African languages easier. What was called a preposition in earlier descriptions of a given language is now referred to, e.g., as "possessive definites", as in Somali (Bell 1953:73), or as "nominaux employés comme premier terme d'un syntagme complétif à relation naturelle..." in Ngambay-Moundou, although the author of the Ngambay-Moundou grammar admits that these units "...traduisent commodément nos prépositions françaises..." (Vandame 1963:114). But this is not the only kind of terminological variation relating to adpositions, as the following observations will show.

Terminological confusion as to what an adposition is, exists not only cross-linguistically but also with reference to one and the same language. In Hausa, a Chadic language, for instance, elements like *cikin* 'in(side), among', *gàban* 'in front of', *baayan* 'behind, after' are called nouns by Kraft and Kirk-Greene (1973:87-89) but prepositions by Taylor (1959:74), and in the literature on Manding and other Mande languages of the Niger-Congo family, the same units are referred to as postpositions by some authors and as relational nouns by others. Bird (1978; 1982), for example, claims that the postpositions of Vai, a Mande language spoken in Liberia, have none of the characteristics of nouns, they do not permit modification or relativization, i.e., they do not take demonstratives, numerals, or markers of referentiality, and he concludes that nouns and postpositions should be considered homophones that are related diachronically but must be treated as discrete syntactic taxa synchronically. Welmers (1976), on the other

hand, maintains that Vai "postpositions" are nominals in all of their functions.

This is but one instance of the confusion surrounding the terminology of adpositions. A few examples may give an impression of the overall situation found in African linguistics.

There are, e.g., those who call "prepositions" "nouns" or "nouns" "prepositions". Migeod (1908) observes for Mende, a Mande language of Sierra Leone, that "A large number of the words used as prepositions are actually nouns...", and according to Taylor (1959:74) in Hausa "The Nominal Prepositions are really nouns...". Note also the following statement from Welmers (1973:453): "Similarly, relational nouns with locative meaning in the Mande languages are commonly thought to be merely or primarily preposition-like, though they may be called "postpositions"..."

Others again treat one word class as subordinate to another. Innes (1971:63) for example defines the postpositions of Mende as "a sub-group of nouns "which differ from other nouns, e.g., in that they are...always indefinite singular."

Not a few students of African languages have recourse to comparative, cross-linguistic considerations in order to characterize adpositions. Thus, we are informed that the relational nouns of Hausa "...are regularly used in contexts in which English-speakers expect a preposition or conjunction" (Kraft & Kirk-Greene 1973:87), that the function of postpositions in Mandinka "...is very similar to that of Prepositions in English" (Rowlands 1959:111), that "where English uses prepositions, Kanuri uses nouns and case suffixes..., or postpositions..." (Lukas 1937:143), that certain nominals of Ngambay-Moundu "...traduisent commodément nos prépositions françaises..." (Vandame 1963:114), or that Lugbara has a group of "positional words corresponding in meaning to our English prepositions" (Barr 1965:64).

What is obvious from statements like these is that in many African languages adpositions, or adposition-like elements, are linked with nouns in some way or other. Many authors have pointed out that adpositions, or a sub-set of them, are "homophonous", or "homonymous" with nouns (cf. Arnott 1970:420 for Fula), and Lébikaza (1985:250/251) describes the postpositions of Kabiye, a Voltaic language of north-central Togo as forming a continuum stretching from local nouns at the one end to postpositions at the other. We shall come back to this position in Section 5.

In addition to these synchronic accounts there are others which introduce diachronic considerations into grammar in order to cope with adpositions. Thus, adpositions of a given language which are described by one author as being "homophonous" with nouns are claimed to be "historically derived" from nouns by other authors.

Spears (1972:16), for instance, notes that in Manding "many of the locative postpositions are obviously cognate with names for parts of the body and further research may reveal that most if not all locative postpositions are derived from body parts," and Brauner (1974:45) states that these postpositions are apparently derived from "old genitive combinations". Similarly, the postpositions of Krongo, a Kordofanian language, are interpreted by Reh (1985:287/288) as being "historically nouns in the locative case", and Migeod (1908) claims that the prepositions of Mende are "probably nouns by origin."

These are but a few examples which may give an impression of the kind of problems linguists have encountered while dealing with adpositions in African languages. Many more instances of peculiar uses of the term "preposition" or of peculiar terminologies for labelling the adpositional concepts looked at in this paper could be added. One might mention the practice of some Cushitists to refer to the "preverbs" of Somali (Bell 1953:20/21) or Arbore (Hayward 1984:309) as prepositions, or of Tucker (1940:247-262) who extends the term "(verb) preposition" to

a variety of word classes in the Central Sudanic languages of the Moru-Madi group, such as tense-aspect markers, adverbs or ideophones.

To summarize, the term "preposition" or "adposition" has been employed for various semantic, syntactic, morphological or other purposes, to the extent that it is impossible to discover any common denominator. Not even the fact that adpositions, as opposed to affixes, form separate words or particles does not seem to be generally agreed upon. Alone-Stokes (1959:28) for instance observe that the "inseparable prepositions" of Amharic, like *ya-* 'of', *la-* 'to, for', etc., are "prefixed to the noun". There are some authors who claim that there are languages without adpositions (cf. Welmers 1973:453) while others hold the opposite view, i.e., that there are no languages without adpositions.⁴

Our main interest in this paper is to investigate how the relational concepts ON, UNDER, IN, FRONT and BACK are encoded as linguistic units governing noun phrases. Unless necessary, the use of these concepts as adverbs, preverbs, etc., will be ignored. Furthermore, whenever possible we will also ignore whether these concepts relate to a subpart (e.g., *on the table*) or the space adjacent to the reference object (*above the table*), although we have to come back to this distinction when dealing with problems of conceptual transfer (see Sections 3 and 5.2).

2.2 Types of adpositions

Among the many distinctions that may be relevant to a typology of adpositions there is one which we will refer to as a distinction between "VA-" and "AN-adpositions".⁵

4. Cf. Kahr (1975:43): "All languages studied, however, possessed at least *one* "primitive" adposition which defies further etymological or syntactic analysis. It appears that no language, no matter how highly inflected, lacks such elements."

VA-adpositions are used to introduce oblique case expressions or participants within the verb phrase or clause, i.e., they are required whenever adjuncts, rather than complements or inherent cases, are presented. AN-adpositions on the other hand do not concern the syntax of the clause, their main function can be seen in expressing spatial, temporal or other orientation relating to the noun phrase. While the semantic properties of the two types of adpositions overlap to some extent, one may say that VA-adpositions typically describe location or movement with reference to a given object, whereas AN-adpositions typically describe the location of an object vis-à-vis some other object. From this characterization it follows that whenever such a distinction is relevant, VA-adpositions imply either a movement or a state whereas AN-adpositions invariably imply a state only. This might be a result of their respective geneses since usually the former originate from verbs whereas the latter derive from nouns (see below).⁶

Another difference relates to the size of class membership. The number of VA-adpositions tends to be limited -- in many languages there exists only one -- whereas AN-adpositions are more numerous, and in not a few grammars their membership is described as open-ended.⁷

Like modern European languages, most African languages do not distinguish morphologically between these two types, the existing set of adpositions combining the properties of

5. These terms stem from Lehmann (1982:75) who calls the relation between a verb and its adverbial relator the "VA relation" and the relation between an adverbial relator and the NP the "AN relation".

6. There are a number of ways in which verb-derived adpositions may develop (cf. Kahr 1975:33). The little information we have on the growth of VA-adpositions suggests that they appear to derive from serial-verb-type constructions.

7. This applies of course only to languages which distinguish the two types of prepositions morphosyntactically (see below).

both. In such languages, certain distinctions are not formally expressed. For instance, there is no morphological difference between inherent and adjunctive clause participants. Sentences like (1) and (2) have the same kind of case coding although (1) contains an inherent and (2) an adjunctive adverbial phrase:

(1) He lives in Paris.

(2) He sings in Paris.

There are, however, some African languages which show a clear distinction between the two types of adpositions. In Maasai and other dialects of the Maa language, for example, there is one VA-adposition, *tɛ* 'at',⁹ as opposed to ten or so AN-adpositions, like *dukóya* 'in front', *atua* 'in', etc. (see Heine & Claudi 1986:100ff.). Similarly, in Ewe the VA-adposition *le*⁹ contrasts with roughly a dozen AN-adpositions like *dzi* 'above', *té* 'below', etc. What the VA-adpositions of Maa and Ewe have in common is:

(1) They have a wide range of case functions, like PLACE, TIME, CAUSE, INSTRUMENT, MANNER, PURPOSE (see Heine & Claudi 1986:102-103; Westermann 1907), they are translated typically as "multi-purpose" prepositions.¹⁰

(2) They may be, and frequently are, combined with AN-adpositions, e.g.,

Maa (Samburu dialect)

3. *tɛ* is a multi-purpose preposition which is used for all kinds of locative, temporal, conditional, manner and other functions. See Heine & Claudi 1986:102.

9. *le* is a locative verb 'be (at)' (see Section 5) which has been grammaticalized to an adposition on the one hand and to a progressive marker on the other.

10. In Maasai for instance, Tucker and Mpaayei (1955:42; 278) translate *tɛ* by means of the following English prepositions: 'with', 'for', 'at', 'by', 'in', 'to', 'among'.

k-é-wwón te sedí é n-kají.
 k-3-stay at behind of FEM-house

'He stays behind the house.'

Ewe

é no déha le xɔ megbé.
 3 drink palm wine at house behind

'He drank palm wine behind the house.'

(3) As these examples indicate, the VA-adposition invariably precedes the AN-adpositions. In Ewe the VA-adposition precedes whereas AN-adpositions follow the noun phrase they govern.

(4) The use of a VA-adposition signals the presence of an adjunct or optional participant, rather than a complement or obligatory participant. Compare the following sentences:

COMPLEMENT (no VA-adposition)	ADJUNCT (with VA-adposition)
Maa (Samburu dialect)	
k-e-éwo enē. k-3-come here	k-é-wwón t-ené. k-3-stay at-here
'She came here.'	'She stays here.'
Ewe	
é vá aff. 3 come here	é ɖu nú le aff. 3 eat thing at here
'She came here.'	'She ate here.'

Linguistic handbooks rarely make it clear what exactly is meant by "preposition", i.e., whether this term covers both types of entities (the VA- and the AN-adposition) or only one and if only one then which of the two. Frequently, however, there is some kind of definition or descriptive statement which helps one to understand the position of the relevant author. Robins (1964:227), for instance, appears to think of AN-adpositions only when characterizing English prepositions: "Thus among English invariables some words (e.g. *at, with, from*) precede nouns to form groups substitutable for adverbs ..."

In the remainder of this paper we will not be dealing with VA-adpositions in great detail, rather, our main concern will be with a small set of AN-adpositions.

3 Conceptual transfer

In the following discussion on strategies for encoding adpositional concepts we will be confined to what Clark (1973) refers to as *P-space*, i.e., space as it is cognitively structured or perceived, rather than to *L-space*, the language of spatial relations (cf. Tanz 1980:32), although our evidence is exclusively linguistic.¹¹ Our observations rely on a sample of 125 African languages selected on the basis of linguistic (both typological and genetic) and geographical criteria.

Our approach is essentially "etic", rather than "emic", and we will aim at cross-cultural generalizations and ignore cultural diversity wherever possible. A few remarks, however, may be of interest for a better understanding of how spatial orientation is perceived and linguistically expressed in some African societies.

For instance, there are a number of striking differences in the way front-back orientation is conceptualized. In European languages, objects without intrinsic fronts and backs, i.e., "frontless" (Tanz 1980:17) or "non-featured" objects like mountains or stones,¹² are conceived of as facing the speaker or deictic centre. Thus, if I say *The rock is in front of the mountain*, the rock is located between the mountain and myself since the mountain

11. For not a few linguists the distinction between a cognitive/conceptual and a linguistic/semantic perspective is largely, or entirely, irrelevant. Research on language acquisition and language development, on the other hand, has established that such a distinction may be significant (cf., e.g., Nelson 1974), and we will adopt the latter position.

12. The opposite would be "fronted" or "inherently featured" reference objects like animals, houses, cars, or chairs.

is assumed to face me. In many African languages, on the other hand, such objects are conceived of as facing in the same direction as the speaker or deictic centre.¹³ With reference to our example this means that since the mountain is "looking" in the same direction as I, it turns its "back" to me, and a rock between the mountain and myself is *behind*, rather than in front of the mountain. Accordingly, a Swahili sentence like

Ng'ombe wako mbele ya mlima.
cattle are front of mountain

which implies that the cattle are invisible for the speaker since they are located on the opposite, i.e. the remote, side of the mountain,¹⁴ has to be translated 'The cows are behind the mountain.'

Furthermore, a number of objects which are perceived as "frontless" in western societies are said to have intrinsic fronts and backs in some African societies. The concept TREE for instance is a much quoted example of a "frontless" object in psycholinguistic writings. Yet in some parts of Africa it is treated as intrinsically fronted. Among the Chamus, an Eastern Nilotic-speaking group of the Maa people, the front of a tree is located on the side toward which its trunk is inclined. If the trunk is perceived as being absolutely vertical then the front is in the direction of either where the biggest branch or the largest number of branches are, in that order.

13. Such languages are, for instance, Hausa, Swahili, Turkana, Karimojong and Maasai.

14. No information is available as to how many languages exactly behave in this way. In So, a Kuliak language of northeastern Uganda, one dialect (Tepes) does, while a second dialect (Kadam) shows the same deictic orientation as western languages.

3.1 Source models

According to Svorou (1986:523) there are three classes of nouns that can become markers of locative relations:

- the body-part class ('head', 'mouth', 'back', etc.),
- the object-part class ('front', 'top', 'edge', 'middle', etc.),
- the environmental landmark class ('sky', 'canyon', 'field', 'house', etc.).

Our survey of African languages, limited to five spatial concepts (ON, UNDER, FRONT, BACK, and IN) only, suggests a typology of essentially two source domains, one domain we will simply refer to as *landmarks*, containing entities like 'earth, soil' and 'sky', and the domain of *body parts* like 'head', 'breast', 'belly' or 'back'. There is a third group of concepts which appears to be included in Svorou's object-part class. It contains items like 'top', 'front', 'bottom', 'back', and 'inside' which show no distinct physical contours but exclusively refer to spatial relations. Items belonging to this group, which we shall simply refer to as "relational concepts", are not treated here as source concepts on the same level with body parts and landmarks, in particular for the following reason: wherever there is sufficient historical information available these concepts turn out to derive either from body parts or from landmarks.¹⁵ The Swahili lexemes *nyuma* 'back' or *chini* 'bottom', which also occur as adverbs and prepositions, are examples of such relational terms. On the synchronic level they do not show any resemblance to other

15. The opposite can be observed as well, but this seems to be due to a different kind of cognitive activity which we refer to as "taboo metaphor". For instance, the Swahili word for FRONT, *mbele*, which derives from a combination of the locative class 18 prefix **mu-* and the noun stem *-wele* 'breast', in some dialects has acquired the meaning 'male sexual organs'. Although we are dealing here with a hypothetical metaphorical development **body part > spatial concept > body part*, this development appears to be due to two different types of metaphor (cf. Claudi & Heine 1986:299-300).

lexemes; they are however historically derived from the Proto-Bantu lexemes *-nũmá 'back' and *-cĩ 'earth, soil' (plus the locative suffix *-ni), respectively.

Accordingly, we shall distinguish two kinds of models serving as the source for the expression of the spatial concepts ON, UNDER, FRONT, BACK and IN, the landmark model and the body part model.

3.1.1 The landmark model

There are only two landmarks figuring in our sample of 125 languages which are of any statistical significance: the concept 'earth' ('soil', 'ground'), which forms the source for UNDER, and 'sky' ('heaven', 'space above') which forms the source for ON. Other concepts, like 'field' (for FRONT) or 'hole' (for IN), have been found in isolated languages only (see 3.1.5).

3.1.2 The body part model

What appears to form the physical base for the body part model is the location of body parts of a human being in upright position (cf. Reh 1985b:4). Parts of the body offer an obvious potential, and they are in fact exploited as the primary means, for spatial orientation. Table 1 shows the most important parts of the body employed for the expression of spatial concepts (the numbers refer to the frequency of occurrence of the relevant body part in our sample of 125 African languages).

TABLE 1: SOURCE CONCEPTS OF THE BODY PART MODEL
(Sample: 125 African languages)

<i>Body part</i>	<i>Spatial concept</i>				
	ON	UNDER	IN	FRONT	BACK
Head	40			6	
Back	2				80
Face	2			47	
Shoulder	2				
Buttock/anus		22			22
Foot		4			1
Belly/stomach			58		
Heart			2		
Eye				14	
Forehead				8	
Mouth				6	
Breast				6	
Chest				2	
Palm of hand			3		

Note that some body parts, in particular 'head' and 'buttock/anus', are exploited for entirely different reference points of spatial orientation. A partial explanation for this is volunteered in 3.1.3.

There are certain parts which are rarely or never used for the kind of spatial orientation considered here. Among these are parts of the head such as the nose, hair, or chin, or body parts such as arm, hand, or knee. Others again are employed time and again throughout the continent, some in an almost predictable way, as we shall see in 3.2.

3.1.3 The pastoralist (animal) model

We noted that the human body forms the main source for the type of spatial concepts considered here. There is, however, an alternative model: one which is derived from the animal body. Its occurrence appears to be largely confined to pastoralist societies of Eastern Africa, i.e., to ethnic groups typically leading a nomadic life whose survival

depends on animal husbandry. These include Western Nilotic, Eastern Nilotic and Eastern Cushitic peoples inhabiting the semi-arid and arid lands of East and Northeast Africa. The pastoralist (animal) model is said to be present when the relation between a spatial concept and the location of a given body part cannot be accounted for in terms of the human body but rather in terms of the body of a four-legged animal. We will assume that this is the case in particular when

- ON is metaphorically derived from 'back',
- FRONT from 'head', and
- BACK from 'buttock' or 'anus'.

The following evidence may be adduced in favour of this model (cf. Reh 1985b:5ff.):

(1) In Dinka, a Western Nilotic language, the term *nhom* 'head' refers to both ON and FRONT (Nebel 1954:423).

(2) In Shilluk, another Western Nilotic language, ON is expressed by both the body parts *wic* 'head' and *kwom* 'back'.

(3) In Somali, an Eastern Cushitic language, the term *dul-* refers to both 'back' and ON.

(4) For Western Nilotic, a noun **tha(a)r* 'buttock, anus' can be reconstructed which frequently turns up with the locative meaning UNDER, but in Shilluk (> *tha*) and Acholi (> *te*) it also refers to BACK.

(5) In Maasai, the nouns *o-siadi* and *ol-kurum*, both meaning 'anus', have been grammaticalized to adverbs and prepositions denoting BACK, and the noun *en-dukóya* 'head' to FRONT (Tucker & Mpaayei 1955:43).

It should be emphasized however that while there are languages which derive concepts of spatial orientation exclusively from human body parts, no language has been found which exclusively relies on the animal body. In all languages of the pastoralist societies concerned there are

at least some instances where the human model co-exists with the animal model. The presence of competing models in these societies may have linguistic implications of the following kind (Reh 1985:9):

(a) One and the same spatial concept may be lexically derived from two different body parts. Thus in Shilluk the concept ON is expressed by either *kwom* ('back'; animal model) or *wi* (< *wic* 'head'). In Chamus, a dialect of the Eastern Nilotic Maa language, BACK is expressed by both *siadfi* ('anus'; animal model) and *orión* (< *n-korión* 'back'; human model).

(b) Conversely, one and the same body part lexeme may refer to divergent spatial concepts. The Dinka noun *nhom* 'head' for instance has given rise to the expression of two concepts, FRONT (animal model) and ON (human or animal model), and in Chamus *siadfi* may be used for the expression of both BACK (animal model) and UNDER (human model).

3.1.4 Other conceptual transfers

The entities figuring in transfers from concrete to spatial concept are also used for other metaphorical transfers. More common directions include the following:

'head'	>	'source of river'
'earth, ground'	>	'country, world'
'eye'	>	'face'
	>	'spring (of water)'

Depending on the language concerned, the conceptual transfer from 'eye' to 'face' may be achieved without involving any morphological marking.¹⁶ Thus, in Bambara *nyé*

16. This appears to be a transfer which is also widespread outside Africa. Thus, Brown & Witkowski (1983a) note: "...a common way of lexically encoding the body part face is through expansion of eye terms."

denotes not only 'eye' but also 'face', as well as 'in front'. Not infrequently, however, 'face' is derived from 'eye' by adding some locative marker. In Ewe, for instance, the noun *ɲkúme* 'face' is composed of *ɲkú* 'eye' plus the locative suffix *-me* 'inside'. Similarly, in Luba the noun *d-ísu* (class 5) 'eye' changes its meaning to 'face' once it enters either of the locative classes 17 (*ku-ísu*) or 18 (*mù-ísu*; Kuperus & Ilunga 1987:82/83).

3.1.5 Some general notes

Table 2 summarizes the frequency of occurrence of the various types of source concepts in our 125 sample languages.

TABLE 2: QUANTITATIVE DISTRIBUTION OF TYPES OF SOURCE CONCEPTS
(Sample: 125 African languages)

	ON	UNDER	IN	FRONT	BACK	Total
<i>Source concept</i>						
Body parts	46	26	63	83	103	321
Landmarks	34	50	1	1	0	86
"Relational concepts"	28	24	30	18	1	101
Other sources	1	4	3	7	2	17
No etymology available	23	24	21	8	15	91
No data available	2	6	9	17	13	47
Total	134	134	127	134	134	663

This table suggests that the body part model forms by far the most important source for the expression of the relevant spatial concepts (see below). The grouping "Other sources" includes eight verbs. That the total of source concepts (134 in all cases concerned) exceeds the number of the 125 sample languages is due to the fact that in some languages a given spatial concept is derived from more than one model. In the following, the various spatial concepts

are briefly considered in turn. "Relational concepts" are not discussed here for reasons to be given below.

ON: In 40 out of 46 cases where body parts are involved the relevant part is 'head'. Other body parts appear to be unimportant, figuring no more than twice: 'face' (2 (times)), 'back' (2; see 3.1.3), and 'shoulder' (2). In all 34 instances where a landmark is involved this is the concept 'sky' (or 'space above', 'heaven', etc.). "Relational concepts" are usually referred to in descriptions of African languages by means of labels like 'top', 'surface', 'upper part' and the like. In some languages there are competing terms for ON, where one is derived from a body part (usually 'head') and the other from a landmark ('sky').

UNDER: In the vast majority of cases (22) where a body part is involved this is 'buttock' and/or 'anus'. Perhaps surprisingly, 'foot' and/or 'leg' figures only in 4 instances as a source concept. The landmark is in all 50 cases a concept that is referred to variously as 'ground', 'earth', or 'soil'.¹⁷ "Relational concepts" are translated variously as 'bottom', 'lower part', 'underside', 'fundament', etc. In languages where there is more than one source domain these are in most cases 'buttock' and 'ground/earth'. In three cases the source for UNDER is 'root'.

IN: Body parts (63 cases) account for the majority of source concepts for IN. By far the most important body part is 'belly/stomach', the only other parts mentioned being 'palm of hand' (3) and 'heart'. The landmark model is statistically negligible in the case of IN, only one language makes use of it.

17. Further meanings of the relevant lexical item include in a number of cases 'land', 'country', or 'world' (see above).

FRONT: By far the most important source for this concept is the body part 'face' (41 cases), followed by 'eye' (11), 'head' (6; see 3.1.3), 'mouth' (6), 'breast' (6), 'forehead' (5) and 'chest' (2). With three cases each, the source appears to be a more complex concept translated variously as 'face/eye' or 'face/forehead'. Perhaps the most noteworthy observation is that in six cases the source concept appears to be a verb ('to be/go ahead'). The landmark model is insignificant as a source; only one language has been reported, where FRONT might be lexically derived from the noun 'field'.

BACK: This concept is invariably derived from body parts, the most important being 'back' (73 cases), 'buttock' (15), or '(nape of) neck' (5). In seven additional cases, the source is rendered semantically as 'back/buttock'.

3.2 Generalizations

The quantitative data presented above show some clear patternings. In Table 3 they are re-arranged with reference to the choice of source models.

TABLE 3: THE CHOICE OF SOURCE MODELS
(The percentages in parentheses refer to the total of 125 African languages)

<i>Spatial concept</i>	<i>Landmark model</i>	<i>Body part model</i>
ON	34 (27.2 %)	46 (36.8 %)
UNDER	50 (40 %)	26 (20.8 %)
IN	1 (0.8 %)	63 (50.4 %)
FRONT	1 (0.8 %)	83 (66.4 %)
BACK	0	102 (81.6 %)

This quantitative distribution allows for the following generalizations:

(1) The five spatial notions considered here may be divided into two types. On the one hand there are the weakly deictic concepts ON and UNDER which are derived in much the same way both from landmarks and from body parts. On the other hand there are the strongly deictic concepts IN, FRONT and BACK which are almost exclusively derived from body parts.

(2) Within these two types of spatial notions, there are again differences with regard to the extent to which these concepts derive from the two source models. Thus, UNDER is much more strongly associated with the landmark model than ON, and BACK is more strongly associated with the body part model than any of the other spatial concepts.

(3) On the whole, the body part model is more important than the landmark model. There appears to be no African language which derives all five concepts from landmarks, while a number of languages have been found relying exclusively on the body part model, i.e., which derive all five concepts from this model (see 3.3 below).

(4) Not infrequently, one and the same spatial concept may be derived from more than one model. In para. 3.1.3, for instance, we have drawn attention to the fact that the body of humans and that of four-legged animals may provide competing source models. More frequently, such competition can be observed between the landmark model and the body part model. Thus, in Ewe the postpositions *dzi* (< *'sky') and *ta'-me* (< *'head-in') are derived from the landmark and the body part model, respectively. Both mean 'on, above' and are largely synonymous in sentences like the following (see Section 5):¹⁸

18. In other contexts, these postpositions show a slightly divergent semantics.

é le ßu-á dzi. 'It is on top of the car.'
it be car-DEF ON

or é le ßu-á ta'-me.
it be car-DEF ON

In Table 4 some of the more common cases of this kind to be observed in African languages are presented:

TABLE 4: INSTANCES OF DUAL SOURCES
FOR SPATIAL CONCEPTS
(Sample: 125 African languages)

<i>Spatial concept</i>	<i>Landmark model</i>	<i>Body part model</i>	<i>Examples of languages</i>
ON	'sky'	+ 'head'	Bongo, Gbari, Kalenjin, Nupe, Maasai, Nubian, Sango, Yulu, Ewe
UNDER	'ground'	+ 'buttock'	Kara, Kera, Yulu, Mursi
FRONT		'head' + 'face'	Lugbara, Murle
BACK		'back' + 'buttock'	Aja, Herero, Kurumba, Luo, Maasai, Nubian

These are but a few observations on the source of the notions ON, UNDER, IN, FRONT, and BACK. In conclusion, one more far-reaching generalization should be added. We observed in (2) above that these notions differ considerably in the extent to which they derive from the landmark and the body part model, respectively. Our survey suggests that they can be arranged on an implicational scale of the following kind with regard to the choice of these two models:

UNDER > ON, IN > FRONT > BACK.

This scale involves the following implication: IF ANY OF THESE SPATIAL CONCEPTS IS DERIVED FROM THE BODY PART MODEL, THEN NONE OF THE CONCEPTS TO ITS RIGHT MAY BE DERIVED FROM

THE LANDMARK MODEL. For instance, if UNDER derives from a body part then neither ON, IN, FRONT nor BACK may have a landmark as their source, i.e., they are likely to derive from body part concepts as well. Similarly, if ON and/or IN derive from a body part then FRONT and BACK are likely to do so as well.¹⁹ In our sample of 125 languages there is only one language which contradicts this pattern.²⁰

3.3 Some typological observations

There is considerable inter-linguistic variation in the way source concepts are selected and treated. We have drawn attention, for instance, to the fact that there are a number of languages which rely exclusively on the body part model, i.e., which derive all five concepts (ON, UNDER, IN, FRONT and BACK) from body parts (see 3.2). This applies in particular to the Western Nilotic languages of the Nilo-Saharan family (Dinka, Shilluk, Jur, Alur, etc.), and we shall therefore refer to this pattern as the *Western Nilotic pattern*.²¹ Languages having this pattern tend to show the following etymologies:

19. In a number of cases "relational concepts" like 'top', 'inside/interior', 'front', or 'backside', rather than any of the two models, appear as the source of these spatial notions. As we observed above, there is reason to assume that they derive historically from either landmarks or body parts. Since we frequently do not know which of the two models is involved in such cases, "relational concepts" for which no etymology is available are ignored in this implicational scale.

20. This language is Newole (Thomann 1905).

21. Other languages showing the Western Nilotic pattern are Bagirmi and Lugbara of Central Sudanic (Nilo-Saharan), or Baule of the Kwa group (Niger-Congo).

ON	<	'head'
UNDER	<	'buttock', 'anus', 'foot'
IN	<	'belly', 'stomach'
FRONT	<	'eye', 'face', 'forehead', 'chest'
BACK	<	'back'.

Another common pattern is one where the labels for vertical orientation, ON and UNDER, derive from landmarks whereas the remaining ones, IN, FRONT and BACK, go back to body parts. Since this structure is most widespread among the Bantu languages we will refer to it as the *Bantu pattern*. Typically, languages showing the Bantu pattern have the following etymologies:²²

ON	<	'sky'
UNDER	<	'soil/earth/ground'
IN	<	'belly', 'stomach'
FRONT	<	'eye', 'face', 'forehead', 'breast', 'chest'
BACK	<	'back'.

Another example where genetic-linguistic or geographical boundaries correlate with the conceptual patterning of spatial orientation is provided by the Afroasiatic family of languages, which appears to behave differently from the rest of African languages in the treatment of spatial concepts. As Table 5 suggests,²³ Afroasiatic languages show an unproportionally high number of "relational concepts" like 'top', 'bottom',

22. This applies to certainly more than a hundred Bantu languages, as the data presented in Johnston (1919) show. In some others, deviations of one kind or other can be found. For instance, in certain areas of the Bantu-speaking region, ON is derived from 'head', or else 'sky' and 'head' are in competition as sources for this notion (see 3.2, (4) above). Note that in a number of Bantu languages the source appears to be a "relational concept", although a historical analysis reveals that the relevant lexeme ultimately derives from a noun 'belly' or 'stomach'.

23. The concepts FRONT and BACK are ignored in Table 5 since their behaviour is much the same in all African languages.

or 'interior' where other African languages have terms cognate with either body parts or landmarks. The relative number of "relational concepts" would even be higher if the Chadic sub-family of Afroasiatic were ignored; for instance, all four Afroasiatic languages which derive IN from the body part model are Chadic languages.²⁴ Disregarding Chadic, no Afroasiatic language of our sample derives the concept IN from a body part or a landmark, and in none of these languages does the concept UNDER derive from a body part.

This general finding correlates with the observation made by past generations of typologists according to which Afroasiatic languages differ from other African languages in displaying a synthetic-inflectional morphosyntax. At the same time it would seem to suggest that the Chadic languages differ from the rest of Afroasiatic in their lexical treatment of spatial concepts.

TABLE 5: SOURCE MODELS FOR ON, UNDER AND IN OCCURRING IN THE LANGUAGES OF THE AFROASIATIC FAMILY (percentages)

Source	Afroasiatic languages (18 languages)				Other African languages (107 languages)			
	ON	UNDER	IN	Average	ON	UNDER	IN	Average
Body parts	24	13	25	21	46	28	75	50
Landmarks	17	34	0	17	34	53	1	29
"Relational concepts"	59	53	75	62	20	19	24	21
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

24. In all four cases the relevant body part is 'belly' or 'stomach'. Mention should be made that, wherever there is etymological evidence, "relational concepts" derive from either body parts or landmarks. In all those cases where a "relational concept" is given as the source this means that no alternative etymology has been found.

3.4 Transfer patterns

The impression conveyed in the preceding paragraphs is that the process from the OBJECT to the SPACE domain involves a discrete step, which is characteristic of metaphorical transfers. Although there is sufficient evidence to support a claim to this effect, there is nevertheless an alternative perspective which suggests that we are dealing with a gradual, continuous, rather than a discrete, discontinuous development (see Heine, Claudi & Hünemeyer forthc., 2.4.1). Accordingly, the transition from concrete objects like body parts or environmental landmarks to spatial concepts like BEHIND or ABOVE is marked by a theoretically indefinite number of intermediate steps. There are however a few more prominent points on this continuum, which are, with reference to body parts:

<i>Stage</i>	<i>Conceptual domain</i>
0 Body part of X	OBJECT
I Subpart of X, spatially defined	OBJECT/SPACE
II Space as part of and adjacent to X	SPACE/OBJECT
III Space adjacent to X	SPACE.

An example from Swahili, involving the word *mbele* 'front', may illustrate these stages. Note that there is no more evidence of Stage 0 since the lexeme **-bele* 'breast', from which *mbele* is historically derived, no longer exists as a body part term.²⁵

I *mbele ya gari lake ni nyeusi.*
front of car his is black

'The front part of his car is black.'

25. This lexeme is retained, however, in the animal body part noun *ki-wele* 'udder'. In some Swahili dialects *u-bele* (or *u-wele*) still occurs as a noun denoting 'breast'.

II taa ziko mbele ya gari.
lamps are front of car

'The lamps are on the front part of the car.'

or mbele ya gari lake ni peusi.
front of car his is LOC-black

'The space in front of his car is black.'

III gari liko mbele.
car is front

'The car is in front/ahead.'

4 From cognition to language structure

The way the spatial notions ON, UNDER, IN, FRONT and BACK are encoded linguistically can immediately be derived from the kind of cognitive activity outlined in Section 3, in particular from the conceptualization of these notions in terms of visible, tangible, thing-like entities such as landmarks and body parts. Roughly speaking, this cognitive activity has the effect that a nominal morphosyntax is replaced by, or turns into, an adverbial morphosyntax, but the process is more complex, as we shall see in Section 5. Before looking into this process, here are a few typological notes concerning linguistic strategies employed in African languages for the expression of spatial concepts.

In most languages considered, the phonological or morphological shape of adpositions differs from that of their cognate nouns. Krongo, a Kordofanian language, for instance adds a locative case prefix *kf-* when deriving adverbs and prepositions from nouns (Reh 1985a:287):

NOUN	PREPOSITION or ADVERB
àtì 'belly'	: k-áatì 'inside'
Tá 'frontside'	: kf-Tá 'in front (of)'
tàará 'free field'	: kf-táará 'outside'.

In Maasai on the other hand the nominal gender prefix (*ol-* masc. and *en(k)-* fem.) is dropped to form adverbs or prepositions (see 4.1.3):

NOUN	PREPOSITION or ADVERB
enk-orión 'back, spine'	: orión 'behind'
en-dukúya 'head'	: dukúya 'before, in front (of)'
o-siadí 'anus'	: siadí 'behind'
en-képér 'sky'	: képér 'above'.

These are but a few examples suggesting that languages may use quite divergent means to derive locatives from nouns. In the following we shall look at some of the major strategies employed in order to encode spatial concepts.

4.1.1 "Zero derivation"²⁶

In some languages the transition from a thing-like entity (THING) to a locative notion (SPACE) does not involve any morphological marking, i.e., a noun denoting a body part ('back') or any other concrete object may, in the same way, refer to a spatial notion ('behind'). Usually the context makes it clear which of the two kinds of meaning is implied, but there are cases as well where the relevant lexeme may designate either an object, as in (a), or a spatial relation, as in (b):

Ewe

me kpó xɔ-á me.
I see house-the inside

- (a) 'I saw the inside of the house.'
(b) 'I looked into the house.'

4.1.2 Employing a locative morphology

Other languages again add some marker to the noun, in order to turn it into a locative notion. As we saw above (4.1), Krongo uses the locative case prefix **kf-** for this purpose.

26. This term is adopted from Allan (1986).

In languages having a noun class system, and this applies to roughly half of all African languages, the shift to a locative notion is achieved typically by moving the relevant noun from its inherent noun class to a locative class. This strategy is widely employed in the Bantu languages. In Swahili, for example, the noun stem **-wele* 'breast' received the locative class (18) prefix *mu-* to form a locative word *mbele* 'frontside', and in the case of the noun stem **-ci* 'earth, country' the locative suffix *-ni* (class 16-18) has been employed to form a locative word *chini* 'below, bottom'.

In Gola, A West Atlantic language of Liberia, nouns enter the locative noun class 8 in order to express a locative meaning, e.g. (Regine Fachner, p.c.),²⁷

e-dil (6) 'ground'	:	ko-dil (8) 'under'
won-jwɔc (3) 'back'	:	ko-jwɔc (8) 'behind'
ke-suà 'stomach'	:	ko-suà (8) 'in(to), inside'
won-feiny (3) 'face'	:	ko-feiny (8) 'before'
ko-fuuny (8) 'sky'	:	ko-fuuny (8) 'up'.

4.1.3 Using nouns non-referentially

A number of languages have an obligatory affix on nouns which, however, is deleted when these nouns are used "non-referentially". For instance, in Chamus, a Maa dialect of Eastern Nilotic, nouns delete their gender prefix in many cases of non-referential use, e.g., when figuring in metaphorical expressions. Compare the following sentences:

Chamus

k-é-ibor n-kóóké	:	k-é-ibór ócók
k-3-white fem-belly		k-3-white belly
'its belly is white (e.g., of a goat)'		'he is open-minded, friendly'

27. The numbers added in parentheses refer to the respective noun class.

l-kfna 'breast' : kɪ-ŋár kfna
we-share breast
'We are children of the
same mother'.

Languages of this type are likely to delete the morphological marker/s expressing referentiality, or "non-generic" use (Greenberg 1978), when the relevant noun is used for spatial notions. Thus, in Chamus the noun n-koriŋ 'back' eliminates the gender prefix (n(k-)) when used as a locative adverb or preposition: oriŋ 'behind'.²⁸

4.1.4 Erosion

Mention should also be made of a factor which does not relate to coding strategies but which may also contribute to separating the phonological shape of a locative word from its non-locative source. Once a given word has been desemantized it is likely to be affected by phonological erosion in some way, i.e., it tends to lose in phonetic substance and thereby becomes dissimilar from its source: grammaticalized morphemes tend to be shorter than the morphemes from which they are derived. In a number of Western Nilotic languages, for example, some body part nouns which have developed into locative prepositions have lost their final consonant, e.g.

Luo

NOUN	DERIVED PREPOSITION
ɪch 'stomach'	ɪ 'inside, in'
wich 'head'	wi 'upon, on' (Stafford 1967:16).

28. Concerning other examples, e.g., from Hausa, see Greenberg (1978:71-72).

4.2 The process

4.2.1 From OBJECT to SPACE

In Section 3 we were concerned with the kind of cognitive activity leading from concrete objects like body parts or landmarks to concepts serving spatial orientation. This activity is metaphorical in nature. It involves a transfer from one domain of human experience to another, in that spatial entities are conceptualized in terms of visible, tangible entities. We have referred to these domains by means of the labels SPACE and OBJECT, respectively, and to the cognitive activity linking these two domains as *categorial metaphor* (Claudi & Heine 1986). The consequences this activity has for language structure are considerable. In more general terms the transition from the OBJECT to the SPACE domain triggers the following linguistic changes:

(1) Since concepts of the OBJECT domain are typically encoded as nouns and those of the SPACE domain as adverbials, we witness a transition from nominal to adverbial word classes like adverbs and prepositions.

(2) This morphological transition entails a corresponding syntactic transition from a noun phrase to an adverbial phrase constituent.

In the present section we shall look at these linguistic implications in more detail; for further information see Lehmann (1982:76ff.), Heine & Reh (1984:101), and Heine, Claudi & Hünemeyer (forthc.).

4.2.2 The grammaticalization channel

Soteria Svorou (1986:516) has proposed the following continuum for the morphological evolution of locative expressions:

LEXICAL

GRAMMATICAL

<----->
 noun > genitive > adverb > adposition > bound affix
 construction

Evidence from African languages supports this hypothesis which is largely in line with earlier findings on this subject (cf. Kahr 1975; Heine & Reh 1984). There are, however, two points which suggest minor modifications. Both relate to the role of adverbs in the continuum. The first concerns the development from genitive construction to adverb. In all languages known to us this development leads straight from noun to adverb without involving an intermediate genitive stage. For instance, in the following sentence from Ewe the noun *meɔbɛ* 'back' is used as an adverb ('behind'), as is evident from the lack of any morphology marking referentiality, such as the definite or the indefinite article. There is nothing to support a claim to the effect that the development from the noun 'back' necessarily leads through a stage of genitive construction.

Ewe

é yi *meɔbɛ*. 'He went behind.'
 3 go back

The second point concerns the development from adverb to adposition. A number of languages have been recorded which have undergone this development, including English.²⁹ There are also some African languages belonging to this group.³⁰ This channel however does not seem to be an obligatory one, it does not hold true for the vast majority of languages in our sample. Rather, prepositions are

29. Svorou (1986:520/521) provides examples from English, Greek, and Melanesian Pidgin English.

30. For example, Taylor (1953:59) writes about Fula: "Prepositions have been developed out of adverbs and most of the simple ones are still used as adverbs also, which means that the line of demarcation between preposition and adverb is often very indistinct."

immediately derived from nouns forming the head in genitive constructions.

In some languages this is not easy to prove, if at all. In others again there are some clues, especially the following: once nouns have been "decategorialized" (cf. Hopper & Thompson 1984) to an adverb they may no longer be associated with a genitive/possessive morphology. Now, an adposition derived from a noun which has also given rise to an adverb frequently contains the same genitive/possessive marking as that noun. It would seem hard to explain an evolution of the following kind, as implied by Svorou's continuum:

noun + genitive marking	>	adverb (- gen. mark.)	>	adposition + genitive marking.
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In Swahili, for example, this would mean that the lexeme **juu** 'top, on, above' in a sentence like the one of column A below has given rise to something like B and eventually to C:

A (noun)	B (adverb)	C (preposition)
juu ya mti haina majani. ON of tree has:not leaves	Ndege yuko juu. bird is ON	Ndege yuko juu ya mti. bird is ON of tree
'The tree top has no leaves.'	'The bird is above.'	'The bird is on the tree.'

Such a development would be at variance with the Swahili rule according to which adverbs may not be followed by the genitive marker.

Similarly, it would be difficult to understand why Hausa "prepositions" like in C below are derived from the corresponding adverbs in B, rather than from head nouns of genitive constructions, as in A. The prepositions, but not the adverbs, contain the "referential suffix" **-n** (masc.) and **-r** (fem.), respectively. There would seem to be no reason

for adverbs to adopt a suffix which they are not allowed to take³¹ in order to become prepositions.

A (head noun)	B (adverb)	C (preposition)
ciki-n 'the stomach (of)'	cikii 'inside'	cikin 'in'.
baaya-n 'the back (of)'	baaya 'backwards'	baayan 'behind'.

To conclude, for the African languages studied by us the following grammaticalization channel can be set up:

4.2.3 Types of genitive constructions

Since the kind of prepositional phrases considered here owe their genesis to genitive/possessive constructions, mention should be made at least of the wide range of morphological variation the latter show in African languages. Ignoring word order, in particular, whether the head precedes or follows its modifier, the following appear to be the most common patterns of morphological marking (examples from languages or language groups are added in parentheses):

- (1) The genitive/possessive marking is part of the head noun or noun phrase (e.g., Hausa).

31. Cf. Kraft & Kirk-Greene (1973:137): "Adverbial nominals (i.e., adverbs; a.n.) do not ordinarily take the referential (-n/-r) suffix, except when followed by **nān/nān...**"

(2) The genitive/possessive marking is part of the dependent noun or noun phrase (e.g., Oromo).

(3) Genitive/possessive marking is expressed by a distinct word which, typically, appears between the two constituents concerned (e.g., Bantu languages).

(4) There is no overt marking at all (e.g., So).

Furthermore, the genitive/possessive marker may show agreement in gender, number, person and/or case with the head (Bantu) or the modifier, or with both.³² Finally, attention should be drawn to the fact that a number of African languages have at their disposal two kinds of marking for genitive/possessive structures: one that is associated with a so-called "alienable" domain of concepts, and another one which is confined to "inalienable" and/or compound-like constructions.

This is but a rough indication of the kind of variation found in African languages to encode nominal possession. We only mention this variation in passing, a more detailed analysis of its implications for the grammar of "adpositional expressions" is urgently required.

5 Postpositions in Ewe

As we have seen in Section 2, a number of paradigms have been employed by students of African languages to define the place of adpositions in grammar. The following positions in particular have been maintained:

32. In the Samburu dialect of the Maa language of Eastern Nilotic for instance, there is gender agreement with the head noun and number agreement with the dependent noun, while in Maasai, another dialect of the same language, there is both gender and number agreement with the head noun and number agreement with the dependent noun.

(a) Adpositions, or "prepositions", are words which can be translated by prepositions in a given matrix language, such as English, German or French.

(b) They are homophonous with or similar to nouns.

(c) They are nouns, or form a distinct sub-class of nouns.

(d) They are cognate with nouns.

(e) They are historically derived from nouns.

Each of these positions captures some characteristic of adpositions, but none of them would seem to do justice to their nature. Taken together, however, they reflect parts of the structure underlying adpositions in many African languages. To account for this structure, the following observations have to be taken into consideration:

Firstly, there is an etic/comparative perspective suggesting that "adpositional concepts" like ON, UNDER, IN, FRONT and BACK are linguistically distinguished in some way or other both in European and in African languages (cf. position (a) above).

Secondly, these concepts are linguistically encoded by means of terms derived from "more concrete" concepts, i.e., from nouns for landmarks and body parts, in accordance with the constraints outlined in section 3. This accounts for both the synchronic positions (b) and (c) on the one hand, and for the diachronic interpretation offered in (d) and (e) on the other.

Thirdly, the more the use of these nouns for "adpositional concepts" is generalized, the more they lose in nominal properties and drift away from their respective lexical source. The result is a continuum of decreasing nominality along which any given adposition may be located.

5.1 Morphosyntax

As we have argued elsewhere (Heine, Claudi & Hünemeyer *forthc.*, 2.4.1), in cases like this we are dealing with a linear continuum which should be interpreted more appropriately as a chain rather than a scale. For present purposes, however, we will be confined to breaking up this linear structure into a number of points, each of which exhibits some kind of distinct linguistic behaviour. The postpositions of Ewe used for the expression of the spatial concepts ON, UNDER, IN, FRONT and BACK will serve as an example of such a linear structure.³³ The parameters employed for defining these points are in particular (for each parameter, an abbreviated reference label is added):³⁴

- (1) Ability (+) vs inability (-) to express a morphological number distinction, i.e., typically, to take a plural marker (PL).
- (2) Ability (+) vs inability (-) to take a demonstrative (DEM).

33. In his reference grammar of Ewe, Westermann (1907:52/53) calls these postpositions "local nouns", and he adds: "Since the local nouns are always placed after a noun or pronoun, they are also called postpositions". In order to save space, the meaning of these lexemes is referred to by means of conceptual labels. Depending on the context, each of them may be translated in various ways, i.e.:

dzi, ta'-me ON	= 'top, above, on'
té, go-me UNDER	= 'bottom, below, under, down'
me, do-me IN	= 'inside, in, within'
ngɔ FRONT	= 'front, before, ahead'
meɖé BACK	= 'back of, after, behind'.

For a more detailed analysis of the postposition meɖé, see Heine, Claudi & Hünemeyer *forthc.*

34. The following ordering of parameters may seem odd; it is based on observations on relative degrees of grammaticalization, as is evident, e.g., in Table 6.

- (3) Ability (+) vs inability (-) to take adjectival qualifiers (ADJ).
- (4) Ability (+) vs inability (-) to permit relativization when not qualified by a genitive noun phrase (REL).
- (5) Ability (+) vs inability (-) to form the sentence subject when not being qualified by a genitive noun phrase (SUBJ; cf. (8) below).
- (6) Ability (+) vs inability (-) to take 1st or 2nd person possessive pronouns as modifiers (PRON).
- (7) Presence (+) vs absence (-) of a genitival-subordinating morphology (GEN).
- (8) Ability (+) vs inability (-) to permit relativization when qualified by a genitive noun phrase (REL GEN).
- (9) Ability (+) vs inability (-) to form the sentence subject as the head of a genitive noun phrase (SUBJ GEN; cf. (5) above).
- (10) Ability (+) vs inability (-) to take 3rd person possessive pronouns as modifiers (PRON 3RD; cf. (6) above).

On the basis of these parameters it is possible to set up an index of nominality, i.e., to locate a given adposition along a scale ranging from a prototypical noun to a prototypical adposition: the higher the number of "+", the more nominal traits the relevant adposition has, and vice versa. Accordingly, an adposition showing a "+" with respect to all parameters would be largely indistinguishable from nouns, while a "prototypical adposition" would be one which has "-" in the case of all parameters concerned.

The African languages studied by us vary considerably in the extent to which their adpositions have nominal traits. More importantly, however, variation is also found among the adpositions of one and the same language. The

present case of postpositions in Ewe may serve as an example. Table 6 shows the degree of nominality for the various postpositions used in this language to denote the concepts ON, UNDER, IN, FRONT and BACK. These postpositions are arranged according to their relative degree of nominality. Note that three of these concepts, ON, UNDER and IN, are expressed by means of two postpositions each which, in turn, are composed of two morphemes each: the second morpheme, *me*, also occurs as a simple postposition ('inside'), while the first denotes a body part, *ta'* 'head', (*a)go* 'buttock', and *do* 'belly', respectively.

The genitival morphology mentioned in parameter (7) refers to the "alienable" genitive marker *pé*,³⁵ where "+" means ability and "-" inability to associate with this marker. Thus, the lexeme *me* (IN) has a "+" since it optionally takes the genitive marker *pé*, as in (a), whereas *té* has "-" since it does not permit the use of the genitive marker, as in (b).

- (a) *βu' sia (pé) me le yibɔɔ.*
car this (of) inside be black

'The interior of this car is black.'

- (b) *βu' sia té le yibɔɔ.*
car this bottom be black

'The bottom of this car is black.'

- (c) **βu' sia pé té le yibɔɔ.*

35. Note that body parts belong to the "alienable" category in Ewe. Concerning the peculiar way this language treats the morphological distinction "alienable" vs "inalienable", see Claudi & Heine (1986:316-318).

TABLE 6: DEGREE OF NOMINALITY OF SOME EWE POSTPOSITIONS

	té	me	dzi	ŋɔ	megbé	ta'-ne	gɔ-me	dɔ-me
	UNDER	IN	ON	FRONT	BACK	ON	UNDER	IN
Lexical source:	?	?	?	?	'back'	'head'	'anus'	'belly'
Parameter:								
(1) PL	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
(2) DEM	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
(3) ADJ	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
(4) REL	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
(5) SUBJ	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
(6) PRON	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
(7) GEN	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
(8) REL GEN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
(9) SUBJ GEN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
(10) PRON 3RD	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Note: When used with a 1st or 2nd person pronoun as a modifier (parameter (6)), these lexemes refer to the human body. Thus, *ŋɔ nye* (FRONT my) means 'the front part of my body' and not 'the front of an object which belongs to me'.

The data presented in Table 6 suggest that all locative lexemes share two nominal characteristics: they may be relativized when qualified by a genitive noun phrase (8), they may be used as subject nominals when governing a genitive noun phrase (9), and they may take a third person possessive pronoun as a modifier (10), e.g.,

é dzi kɔ. 'Its top is clean.' (9)
his ON be.clean

mié le é té. 'We are under it.' (10)
we be his UNDER

These lexemes may be distinguished, however, on the basis of their relative degree of nominality. Thus, *té* shows only two nominal features, *me* and *dzi* four, and the remaining lexemes are nominal with reference to all ten parameters, i.e., they are virtually indistinguishable from nouns.

One might have expected that among the parameters proposed there would be at least one relating to the morphosyntactic status of the lexemes concerned: whether they are used as nominal or as adverbial morphemes and, accordingly, whether they govern noun phrases or adverbial phrases. That there is such a distinction is suggested by the kind of pronominal reference these morphemes show. The lexeme *me* (IN) forms the head of a noun phrase in (a) but of an adverbial phrase in (b), as can be derived, e.g., from the fact that *me* would be referred to typically by either *ésia* 'this' or *núká* 'what?' in (a) but by *afimá* 'there' or *afiká* 'where?' in (b).

- (a) *asi-á me kɔ.* 'The market is clean.'
 market-the IN be.clean
- (b) *é le asi-á me.* 'She is at the market.'
 s/he be market-the IN

In most cases, however, *me*, or any of the other postpositions for that matter, may be interpreted at the same time as the head of a noun phrase and of an adverbial phrase, as is the case in (c), where *é me* can be pronominalized by either *núká* 'what?' or *afiká* 'where?':

- (c) *me kpɔ́ é me.* (1) 'I saw its inside.'
 I see its IN (2) 'I looked into it.'

This is an inherent characteristic of transitional stages in grammaticalization: when a new structure (i.e., an adverbial morphosyntax in this example) is introduced, the old structure (a nominal morphosyntax) is still used, the result being *overlapping* (see Heine, Claudi & Hünnemeyer *forthc.*). The questions one might wish to raise now are:

- Why are there doublets of postpositions in the case of the concepts ON, UNDER, and IN, but not in the case of FRONT and BACK?
- Why are there two sets of postpositions, one which consists of one morpheme only and another which is composed of two morphemes?

The data available suggest the following answer. The lexemes *té* (UNDER), *me* (IN) and *dzi* (ON) have been grammaticalized to the extent that they have lost many of their former nominal characteristics. To make up for this loss, the language has developed a new set of lexemes for the expression of the spatial concepts UNDER, IN and ON, respectively. These lexemes have the following in common: they are derived from body parts,³⁶ have the "defective nominal" *me* as their head, and are fully nominal, i.e., they may be used in contexts where *té*, *me* and *dzi* may not.³⁷

It would seem that we are dealing with a kind of "morphological cycle", where nominals are grammaticalized, and the grammaticalized lexemes *té*, *me* and *dzi* are now being replaced by a new set of nominals. Thus there are new means for expressing UNDER, IN and ON in contexts where parameters (1) to (6) apply. With reference to parameters (7) to (9), however, some kind of "synonymy" results, since the old means compete with the functionally equivalent new means. As a consequence, there are two sets of largely synonymous "postpositions": on the one hand the old set consisting of the "defective nominals" *té*, *me* and *dzi*, and on the other hand the new set of the fully nominal lexemes *go-me*, *do-me* and *ta'-me* formed according to a new pattern.

One might ask whether there is any justification to assume that the postpositions *té*, *me* and *dzi* are really derived from nouns. That they in fact are, can be concluded from evidence like the following. When a lexeme is grammaticalized then it tends to survive in its earlier state in a "frozen" form in specific, idiomatic contexts, where its use is no longer "productive". This is exactly

36. As we saw in section 3, the body parts selected are, in fact, the most common ones used in African languages for the expression of the spatial concepts UNDER (< 'buttock'), IN (< 'belly') and ON (< 'head').

37. In a number of cases, particularly in contexts where parameters (1) to (6) apply, our informant gave us responses like the following: "*té* cannot be used in this sentence, the right word would be *gone*."

what has happened with these postpositions. For example, according to Table 6 they may not be pluralized, may not take demonstrative or adjectival qualifiers nor associate with 1st or 2nd person possessive pronouns. Sentences like the following are therefore ungrammatical:

***βu-á le dzi nye.**
car-the be ON my

'The car is above me.'

***me wo le kɔ.**
IN your be clean

'Your interior is clean.'

Almost predictably, however, all three postpositions may be used with 1st or 2nd person possessive pronouns in certain idiomatic expressions, e.g.,

é le dzi nye.
it be ON my

'It is (a burden) on me, it oppresses me.'

dzi le me wo a? ee, é le me nye.
heart be IN your Q? yes, it be IN my

'Are you brave? Yes, I am.'

é po e dé té nye. 'He forced me.'
he beat it toward UNDER my

5.2 Meaning

Some of the semantic characteristics of the Ewe postpositions are summarized in Table 7. These parameters are derived from the cognitive distinctions made in Section 3.4.

TABLE 7: SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS
OF SOME EWE POSTPOSITIONS

Denoting a	té	me	dzi	ngɔ	meɓbé	ta'-me	gɔ-me	dɔ-me
(1) concrete object	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
(2) subpart of X	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
(3) space as part of or adjacent to X	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
(4) Space adjacent to X	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+

Parameter (1) refers to the use of the "postpositions" as visible, tangible objects like body parts, as in (i).

- (i) **meɓbé keke áǵé le é sí.**
BACK broad INDEF be his hand

'He has a broad back.'

This use is likely to be that of the respective source of these "postpositions" (see Table 6).

(2) refers to the spatially defined part of a given object, as in (ii),

- (ii) **xɔ sia pé dzi kɔ.**
house this of ON be.clean

'The top of this house is clean.'

while (3) is intermediate between (2) and (4) in that it refers to space both as part of and adjacent to an object, e.g.,

- (iii) **é le xɔ-á ngɔ.**
s/he be house-the FRONT

'He is at the entrance of the house.'
or 'He is in front of the house.'

Finally, (4) refers exclusively to a location detached from the reference object, as in (iv):

- (iv) **adáka-á le ngo.**
box-the be FRONT

'The box is in front.'

As Table 7 suggests, two of the postpositions do not show the whole range of locative meanings. **dzi** typically refers to the part of an object which is conceived spatially, but not to an adjacent location. Thus, sentence (v)

- (v) **xeví-á le xo-a dzi.**
bird-the be house-the ON

means 'The bird is on the house.', while 'The bird is above the house.' would be translated as (vi), using the second postposition for ON (see 5.1).

- (vi) **xeví-á le xo-á ta'-me.**
bird-the be house-the ON

'The bird is on/over the house.'

té has been grammaticalized to the extent that it is confined to denoting a location adjacent to a reference object, as in (vii).

- (vii) **é le ßu-a té.**
s/he be car-the UNDER

'It is below the car.'

5.3 Summary

These observations suggest that we are dealing with a unidirectional development from noun to adposition which surfaces on the one hand, in the synchronic state of the language, in the form of a linear structure characterised by

a decreasing degree of nominality, and on the other hand in the form of frozen relics as they turn up in certain idiomatic expressions.

The postpositions of Ewe present but one of the many possible examples of the way adpositional systems are structured; we could have chosen any other language from any other region or family in Africa. These examples suggest that a description of "adpositions" in terms of established word classes is likely to miss certain insights about the nature of these units. It would seem that an approach which aims at accounting for "adpositions" has to take observations like the following into account:

(a) "Adpositions" used to express concepts like ON, UNDER, IN, FRONT and BACK owe their genesis to a cognitive process leading from the domain of concrete, object-like concepts to the domain of space. This process is metaphorically structured and has both a discontinuous and a continuous aspect (see Heine, Claudi & Hünnemeyer *forthc.*).

(b) The linguistic result of this process is a development from concrete nouns like body parts and environmental landmarks to locative morphemes, from a word class which may be marked for number, referentiality, gender, case, and which may be modified by adjectives, relative clauses, etc., to one which lacks all these characteristics.

(c) In the synchronic state of a given language, these developments are reflected in the form of a *grammaticalization chain*, i.e., a linear structure which may be described either as a continuum, a scale or a chain. At the one end of this linear structure there are full-fledged concrete nouns, at the other end there are invariable locative morphemes which have little in common with nouns. In order to describe the morphosyntax of a given "adposition", or of a set of "adpositions" in a given language, it is necessary to determine its range of possible uses along this linear structure. This means, for

example, that an Ewe postposition like *té* (UNDER) behaves like a noun with reference to parameters (8) to (10) but not with reference to (1) to (7) of Table 6. In this respect, *té* contrasts with a postposition like *megbé* (BACK), which is nominal with reference to all parameters considered. Similarly, *té* has lost the ability to refer to concrete objects or to the subpart of an object, whereas *megbé* shows the whole range of meanings characteristic of "adpositions" in Ewe, as we have seen in Table 7.

6 Conclusions

The present paper is devoted to the grammaticalization channel leading to the emergence of linguistic expressions for the concepts ON, UNDER, IN, FRONT and BACK, in particular to the relation between the conceptual input and its linguistic output, and the implications this process has for synchronic grammar.

Wherever there is etymological evidence available, the source of these spatial concepts turns out to be a physically defined entity, either a landmark like 'sky' or 'earth/soil/ground', or a body part.³⁸ Linguistically speaking, this means that the lexemes denoting these spatial concepts are derived from concrete nouns. In accordance with the implicational scale proposed in 3.3 it is possible to narrow down the range of possible source items. For instance, if UNDER is derived from a body part item then none of the other four concepts may be derived from a lexeme denoting a landmark. It would seem that this scale, which has the structure

UNDER > ON, IN > FRONT > BACK,

38. Whether a source unit like 'sky' indeed forms a "physically defined entity" might seem controversial, but this does not invalidate the overall observation.

represents one of increasing deictivity, where UNDER is the most weakly and BACK the most strongly deictic. The degree of deictivity correlates with the choice of source models. Thus, UNDER is most frequently associated with the landmark model, ON is less so, and the strongly deictic concepts FRONT and BACK are virtually always derived from the body part model.

There appears to be some correlation between the way source concepts are selected and the relative order in which the spatial notions under discussion evolve in language acquisition.³⁹ In their study of locative expressions in English, Italian, Serbo-Croatian and Turkish, Johnston and Slobin (1979) observe that children between the years of 2;0 and 4;0 in all language groups concerned learned locative adpositions in a consistent order. With reference to the spatial notions considered here, this means that the weakly deictic notions UNDER, ON, and IN are acquired earlier than are the strongly deictic FRONT and BACK (cf. Johnston & Slobin 1979:539-540).⁴⁰

The linguistic expressions used for these spatial concepts tend to exhibit a highly variable morphosyntax which can neither be described satisfactorily in terms of nouns nor of any other word category. Rather, we are dealing with a grammaticalization chain ranging typically from a concrete noun to a pure locative marker. This chain eludes the usual distinction between diachrony and synchrony, it is *panchronic* in nature, although it can be understood both as a diachronic process and as a synchronic structure.

39. We are disregarding all information which is not relevant here, such as the distinction between inherently featured vs non-featured reference objects. Mention should also be made of the fact that the issue under discussion has been the subject of some controversies among psycholinguists.

40. According to Johnston (1984:415), however, children learn to express these notions in the following order: ON > IN > UNDER > BACK > FRONT. This order does not show any correlation with the implicational scale proposed in section 3.3.

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